

Identification of new studies via databases and registers

Identification

Records identified from:
Databases (n = 3):
PubMed (n = 31)
EMBASE (n = 45)
CENTRAL (n = 53)
Registers (n = 0)

Records removed before screening:
Duplicate records (n = 0)
Records marked as ineligible by automation tools (n = 31)
Records removed for other reasons (n = 0)

Screening

Records screened
(n = 98)

Records excluded
(n = 73)

Reports sought for retrieval
(n = 25)

Reports not retrieved
(n = 17)

Reports assessed for eligibility
(n = 8)

Reports excluded:
Does not measure exacerbation data (n = 7)
Use of non-SABA or LABA/ICS agent (n = 7)
Presence of another diagnosis (COPD) (n = 3)

Included

New studies included in review
(n = 8)
Reports of new included studies
(n = 0)